

BOSHQARUVLARI INTEGRAL CHEGARALANISHLI QUVISH DISKRET O'YINIDA II-STRATEGIYANING TADBIQI

Umaraliyeva Nargiza Tashkinbayevna

Namangan davlat universiteti tayanch doktoranti.

Abduraxmanov Azizbek Shokirjon o'g'li

Namangan davlat universiteti o'qituvchisi.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola boshqaruvlari Integral chegaralanishli bitta quvlovchi va bitta qochuvchiga ega diskret o'yinda quvish masalasini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan. Bunda quvish masalasini yechish uchun parallel yaqinlashish metodidan foydalanilgan. Shuning uchun quvlovchiga parallel quvish strategiyasi (qisqacha, II-strategiya) qurilgan va natijada, tutishning yetarli sharti topilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Diskret o'yin, quvish, strategiya, integral chegaralanish, kafolatlangan tutish qadami.

Аннотация. Статья посвящена исследованию задачи преследования в дискретной игре с одним преследователем и одним убегающим с интегральными ограниченными управлениями. Здесь для решения задачи преследования используется метод параллельного сближения. Таким образом, для преследователя строится параллельная стратегия преследования (кратко, II-стратегия) и, как следствие, найдено достаточное условие для поимки.

Ключевые слова: Дискретная игра, преследования, стратегия, интегральное ограничение, гарантированный шаг захвата.

Abstract. This article is devoted to study the pursuit problem in a discrete game with one pursuer and one evader whose controls are subject to Integral constraint. Here the method of parallel approach is used to solve the pursuit problem. Thus the parallel pursuit strategy (in brief, the II-strategy) is constructed for the pursuer, and in consequence, a sufficient condition of capture is found.

Keywords: Discrete game, pursuit, strategy, Integral constraint, guaranteed capture step.

Ushbu masalaning animatsion echimi tadqiqot ishlarda muxim o'rin tutadi va matematik boshqaruv nazariyasini ham fundamental, ham amaliy rivojiga muayyan darajada xizmat qiladi.

\mathbb{R}^n ($n \geq 1$) fazoda boshqariladigan ikkita P va E obyektlar berilgan bo'lib, ularni mos ravishda "quvlovchi" va "qochuvchi" deb ataylik. Bunda P obyekt E obyektini ta'qib qilsin deb faraz qilamiz. Biz P obyektning holat vektorini x orqali, E obyektning holat vektorini esa y orqali ifodalaymiz. U holda, P va E obyektning \mathbb{R}^n fazodagi harakati mos ravishda quyidagi rekurrent tenglamalarga asoslangan bo'lsin:

$$P: x_k = u_k + x_{k-1}, \quad x(0) = x_0, \quad (1)$$

$$E: y_k = v_k + y_{k-1}, \quad y(0) = y_0, \quad (2)$$

bu yerda $x, y, u, v \in \mathbb{R}^n$; k – obyektning qadam nomeri va $k = 1, 2, \dots$; x_0 va y_0 – obyektning mos ravishdagi boshlang'ich holatlari va bunda $x_0 \neq y_0$ bo'lishi talab qilinadi.

(1) tenglamadagi u_k , $k = 1, 2, \dots$, – P obyektning boshqaruv parametri bo'lib, uni $u_k(\cdot): [0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ akslantirishni bajaruvchi o'lchanuvchi funksiya sifatida tanlanadi va quyidagi integral chegaralanishni qanoatlantirishini talab qilamiz:

$$\|u_k(\cdot)\| = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} |u_k|^2 \leq \rho_0, \quad (3)$$

bu yerda $\rho_0 > 0$ bo'lib, P obyekt boshlang'ich resursining qiymatini ifodalaydi.

Xuddi shu kabi, (2) tenglamadagi v_k , $k = 1, 2, \dots$, – E obyektning boshqaruv parametri bo'lib, uni $v_k(\cdot): [0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ akslantirishni bajaruvchi o'lchanuvchi funksiya sifatida tanlanadi va quyidagi integral chegaralanishi talab etiladi:

$$\|v_k(\cdot)\| = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} |v_k|^2 \leq \sigma_0, \quad (4)$$

bu yerda $\sigma_0 \geq 0$ bo'lib, E obyekt boshlang'ich resursining qiymatini ifodalaydi.

Qaralayotgan o'yinda P obyektning asosiy maqsadi E obyektini tutish, ya'ni biror $k^* \in N$ chekli qadamda quyidagi tenglikka erishish:

$$x_{k^*} = y_{k^*}.$$

(1) va (2) tengliklardan ularga teng kuchli bo'lgan quyidagi tengliklarni topish qiyin emas:

$$x_k = x_0 + \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} u_i, \quad y_k = y_0 + \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} v_i, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots \quad (5)$$

Endi $z_0 = x_0 - y_0$, $z_k = x_k - y_k$, $k = 1, 2, \dots$, belgilashlarni kiritaylik. U holda (6) tengliklardan quyidagini hosil qilamiz:

$$z_k = z_0 + \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} (u_i - v_i), \quad k = 1, 2, \dots$$

Tutish masalasini hal qilish uchun avvalo, P obyektga strategiya taklif qilishimiz kerak. Biz bu yerda diskret va differensial o'yinlar nazariyasida obyektning eng tez yaqinlashishni ta'minlaydigan parallel quvish strategiyasini (qisqacha, Π -strategiya) tadbiiq qilamiz.

Ta'rif. (1)–(4) o'yinda P obyektning parallel quvish strategiyasi deb quyidagi rekurrent tenglikka aytamiz:

$$u_k = u_k(v_k) = v_k - \lambda(v_k)\xi_0, \quad (6)$$

bu yerda

$$\lambda(v_k) = \max\left\{0, \frac{\delta_0}{|z_0|} + 2\langle v_k, \xi_0 \rangle\right\}, \quad \xi_0 = \frac{z_0}{|z_0|}, \quad \delta_0 = \rho_0 - \sigma_0.$$

Xossa. Agar $\rho_0 \geq \sigma_0$ shart bajarilsa, u holda (6) formula uchun quyidagi tenglik o'rinli:

$$|u_k|^2 = |v_k|^2 + \lambda(v_k) \frac{\delta_0}{|z_0|}.$$

Teorema. Agar (1)–(4) o'yinda $\rho_0 > \sigma_0$ shart bajarilsa, u holda P obyekt (6) startegiya yordamida E obyektini biror $k \in (0, k_I]$ qadamda tutishi mumkin, bu yerda $k_I = \left\lceil \left(\frac{|z_0|}{\sqrt{\rho_0 - \sigma_0}}\right)^2 \right\rceil$

bo'lib, uni kafolatlangan tutish qadami deb aytamiz.

Quyida (1)–(4) o'yinning tekislikdagi holi uchun grafik (1-rasm) va qiymatlar jadvali (1-jadval) ko'rinishidagi yechimlarini keltiramiz.

1-rasm.

burchak=24,00	n=0	x1=0,0000	y1=0,0000	x2=10,0000	y2=0,0000
burchak=-16,00	n=1	x1=4,6530	y1=1,8303	x2=14,1110	y2=1,8303
burchak=-11,00	n=2	x1=9,4967	y1=0,5899	x2=18,4366	y2=0,5899
burchak=-11,00	n=3	x1=14,4224	y1=-0,2687	x2=22,8540	y2=-0,2687
burchak=-22,00	n=4	x1=19,3481	y1=-1,1273	x2=27,2713	y2=-1,1273
burchak=17,00	n=5	x1=24,0554	y1=-2,8131	x2=31,4436	y2=-2,8131
burchak=-27,00	n=6	x1=28,8792	y1=-1,4974	x2=35,7470	y2=-1,4974
burchak=8,00	n=7	x1=33,4427	y1=-3,5403	x2=39,7565	y2=-3,5403
burchak=-3,00	n=8	x1=38,4034	y1=-2,9141	x2=44,2127	y2=-2,9141
burchak=-14,00	n=9	x1=43,3978	y1=-3,1496	x2=48,7065	y2=-3,1496
burchak=25,00	n=10	x1=48,2779	y1=-4,2382	x2=53,0729	y2=-4,2382
burchak=-20,00	n=11	x1=52,9021	y1=-2,3364	x2=57,1513	y2=-2,3364
burchak=1,00	n=12	x1=57,6593	y1=-3,8755	x2=61,3799	y2=-3,8755
burchak=-26,00	n=13	x1=62,6587	y1=-3,7970	x2=65,8792	y2=-3,7970
burchak=7,00	n=14	x1=67,2531	y1=-5,7697	x2=69,9238	y2=-5,7697
burchak=17,00	n=15	x1=72,2229	y1=-5,2213	x2=74,3902	y2=-5,2213
burchak=-12,00	n=16	x1=77,0467	y1=-3,9056	x2=78,6936	y2=-3,9056
burchak=23,00	n=17	x1=81,9584	y1=-4,8412	x2=83,0953	y2=-4,8412
burchak=-4,00	n=18	x1=86,6390	y1=-3,0829	x2=87,2375	y2=-3,0829
burchak=29,00	n=19	x1=91,6292	y1=-3,3968	x2=91,7266	y2=-3,3968
tutish nuqtasi		x1=95,6623566404554	y1=-1,21516124600119		

1-jadval.

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